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Partnership Initiative for
Sustainable Land Management

Land Cover Trends in SIDS: Supporting UNCCD PRAIS 5 and SDG 15.3.1 Reporting

Comparison of Global Land Cover Datasets and Development of a Land Cover Transition Tool

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Executive Summary

This report presents a **comparative analysis of three globally available land cover datasets**, ESA CCI-LC (300m), GLC-FCS30D (30m), and GLAD Land Cover (30m), in the context of supporting **Small Island Developing States (SIDS) in reporting on SDG Indicator 15.3.1** ("Proportion of land that is degraded") and progress towards **Land Degradation Neutrality, to the United Nations Convention to Combat Desertification** (UNCCD).

While ESA CCI-LC provides full coverage for SIDS, its coarse resolution limits detailed analysis. The finer resolution datasets (**GLC-FCS30D** and **GLAD**) offer greater spatial detail but suffer from incomplete geographic coverage and significant classification discrepancies, particularly in urban, cropland, grassland, and wetland categories.

The study highlights that these differences are mainly due to contrasting classification methods (contextual vs pixel-based) and definitions of land cover types, which significantly affect degradation assessments. Examples from seven countries (**Saint Lucia, Antigua and Barbuda, Trinidad and Tobago, Cape Verde, Barbados, Timor-Leste, and Guinea-Bissau**) illustrate how dataset choice can lead to substantially different national land cover statistics and degradation maps.

To address these challenges, the **Land Cover Transition Tool** was developed in Google Earth Engine by Apacheta and PISLM. It allows users to explore, compare, and analyze land cover transitions across the ESA CCI-LC, GLAD, and GLC-FCS30D datasets for **40 SIDS**, across the required UNCCD reporting periods (2000–2015, 2015–2019, 2015–2023). The tool provides visual comparisons, statistical analysis (e.g., area calculations, transition matrices), and facilitates evidence-based selection of land cover products for reporting.

Link to the tool: <https://apacheta.projects.earthengine.app/view/compare-lct-sids>

General Conclusion

Global land cover datasets perform differently across Small Island Developing States (SIDS), with each country's unique environmental conditions influencing classification accuracy. A product may align well with observed land cover in one country but not in others, and may perform strongly for certain land cover classes while misclassifying others.

However, their suitability for SDG 15.3.1 reporting ultimately depends on **how well they capture land cover changes over time**. Reliable land degradation assessments require not just good classification, but also consistent and meaningful detection of transitions. A high-quality single-year map is insufficient if it leads to misleading degradation results when changes are analyzed.

The report concludes that **careful local evaluation of datasets is critical for accurate SDG 15.3.1 reporting in SIDS**, and that no single product is universally superior. Instead, a case-by-case assessment using tools like the Land Cover Transition Tool is recommended.

Introduction

The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development includes 234 indicators to track progress toward the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Among them, SDG 15.3 aims to combat desertification, restore degraded land and soil, and achieve a land degradation-neutral (LDN) world by 2030. This goal is monitored through Indicator 15.3.1, which measures the “Proportion of land that is degraded over total land area.”

Indicator **15.3.1** is assessed using three key sub-indicators:

1. **Trends in land cover** – evaluating land degradation based on land cover changes
2. **Trends in land productivity** – measuring variations in vegetation growth, and
3. **Trends in carbon stocks** – analysing soil organic carbon dynamics.

The land cover sub-indicator is particularly important for identifying degradation caused by land cover changes. It plays a crucial role in Integrated Land Use Planning (ILUP) by providing essential information for assessing land dynamics, guiding sustainable land management, and optimizing land use strategies. Additionally, land cover monitoring supports synergies among the three Rio Conventions—the United Nations Convention to Combat Desertification (UNCCD), the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC), and the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD). As a transformational variable, land cover changes influence desertification trends (UNCCD), carbon fluxes and climate regulation (UNFCCC), and habitat integrity and biodiversity conservation (CBD), reinforcing the interconnected nature of land degradation, climate change, and ecosystem health.

To fulfil their UNCCD reporting obligations, countries submit data on Indicator 15.3.1 through the Performance Review and Assessment of Implementation System (PRAIS) platform. The Good Practice Guidance (GPG) for SDG Indicator 15.3.1 provides a recommended methodology for assessing land degradation, including the use of a transition matrix to analyse land cover changes over three reporting periods:

- **Baseline period:** 2000–2015
- **Reporting Period 1:** 2015–2019
- **Reporting Period 2:** 2015–2023

The United Nations Convention to Combat Desertification (UNCCD) provides global default datasets for consistency in reporting, but countries are encouraged to use their own national datasets when available. For land cover monitoring, the default dataset is the European Space Agency’s Climate Change Initiative Land Cover (ESA CCI-LC), which offers global coverage at a 300m spatial resolution with annual updates from 1992 to 2020.

However, for Small Island Developing States (SIDS), this resolution may not be sufficient. SIDS are among the most vulnerable nations to land degradation and climate change, facing challenges due to their small land area, fragile soils, and exposure to environmental and economic shocks. Although they

contribute less than 1% of global greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, they disproportionately experience the effects of climate change, such as rising sea level, extreme weather events, and land degradation.

Recognizing these vulnerabilities, LDN has been positioned as a key approach to support SIDS, aligning with both the SIDS Accelerated Modalities of Action (SAMOA) Pathway and the SDGs. Effective implementation of LDN requires evidence-based decision-making, which depends on high-quality geospatial data, robust monitoring systems, and reliable maps. However, most SIDS lack an integrated land degradation monitoring framework, and available global datasets may not provide the necessary spatial detail.

Given the limitations of the ESA CCI-LC 300m dataset, alternative datasets such as Global Land-Cover Product with Fine Classification System at 30 m (GLC-FCS30D) and Global Land Analysis and Discovery (GLAD) land cover offer near-global coverage at 30m spatial resolution, potentially improving land cover change detection in SIDS. These datasets could provide a more accurate basis for tracking SDG 15.3.1 and LDN implementation in small-scale landscapes.

Apacheta and PISLM contributes to this effort by **evaluating GLC-FCS30D and GLAD land cover** within the **PRAIS framework and reporting periods**, assessing their suitability for the **baseline and reporting periods required for the next UNCCD reporting cycle**. Apacheta is also providing a web-based tool that covers 40 SIDS (Table 1) with the aim that each interested Parties can explore all the data available in all the periods required and using a default transition matrix. This assessment will provide insights into whether these **higher-resolution datasets** can serve as viable alternatives for **monitoring land degradation trends in SIDS**, ultimately supporting **evidence-based decision-making and improved LDN implementation**.

Table 1: SIDS analysed in the study and percentage of coverage of each product. Green indicates 100% coverage in three all products, Yellow not completely covered in all products.

SIDS	ESA coverage (%)	GLC-FCS30D coverage (%)	GLAD coverage (%)
Antigua and Barbuda	100	100	100
Bahamas	100	100	100
Bahrain	100	100	100
Barbados	100	100	100
Belize	100	100	100
Cape Verde	100	100	100
Comoros	100	100	100
Cook Islands	100	0	0
Cuba	100	100	100
Dominica	100	100	100
Dominican Republic	100	100	100
Fiji	100	0	95

Grenada	100	100	100
Guinea-Bissau	100	100	100
Guyana	100	100	100
Haiti	100	100	100
Jamaica	100	100	100
Kiribati	100	0	0
Maldives	100	100	86.5
Marshall Islands	100	0	0
Mauritius	100	92.41	93.09
Micronesia (Federated States of)	100	0	0
Nauru	100	0	0
Niue	100	0	0
Palau	100	0	100
Papua New Guinea	100	95.05	100
Saint Kitts and Nevis	100	100	100
Saint Lucia	100	100	100
Saint Vincent and the Grenadines	100	100	100
Samoa	100	0	0
Sao Tome and Principe	100	100	0
Seychelles	100	52.91	43.7
Singapore	100	100	100
Solomon Islands	100	0	100
Suriname	100	100	100
Timor-Leste	100	100	100
Tonga	100	0	0
Trinidad and Tobago	100	100	100
Tuvalu	100	0	0
Vanuatu	100	0	100

Chapter 1: Products comparison

Available products

Several global land-cover datasets have been developed to analyse changes in land use and vegetation over time. Among these, two products stand out due to their detailed classification systems and extensive temporal coverage: the GLAD Land Cover and the GLC-FCS30D. This is a big resolution improvement from the ESA 300m product that was the default land cover dataset of the UNCCD PRAIS reporting. These 30m datasets provide valuable information on forest extent, cropland, built-up areas, and other land-cover types, utilizing machine learning techniques to improve classification accuracy. Below is a brief description of each product, including their main characteristics, spatial resolution, and coverage. We analysed a total of 40 SIDS (Table 1) and not all of them are covered in the same proportion by all products. The ESA 300m is the only one that covers 100% of the 40 SIDS area. A total of 23 SIDS is fully covered by the two 30m products, 5 are fully covered by one of them and 12 are not fully covered by any of them (Table 1).

ESA CCI Land Cover

The ESA Climate Change Initiative (CCI) Land Cover dataset provides 22 land cover classes, at 300 m resolution based on 300m MERIS, 1 km Spot vegetation, 1 km Proba-V and 1 km AVHRR data. Annual updates of the CCI-LC product are currently available from 1992 to 2020. This product is available for all 40 SIDS, covering 100% of their surface area (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1: Screenshot of original ESA CCI Land Cover on Guinea-Bissau.

The Global Land Analysis and Discovery (GLAD) Land Cover

The GLAD Land Cover product is part of a comprehensive study aimed at quantifying changes in land cover and land use over two decades, from 2000 to 2020. This dataset provides information on forest extent and height, cropland, built-up areas, surface water, and the extent of perennial snow and ice. To achieve this, each global thematic map was generated independently using regionally and locally calibrated machine learning models (Potapov et al., 2022). The classification process resulted in a total of 110 distinct classes, which account for variations in tree height (for forested areas), the percentage of a given vegetation class at the pixel level, and the proportion of Landsat observations classified as water throughout the year. In contrast, categories such as cropland, built-up areas, snow/ice, and ocean are classified as single units without subcategories (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2: Screenshot of original GLAD Land Cover on Antigua Island.

This product is available in five-year intervals, covering the period from 2000 to 2020, with a spatial resolution of 30 meters per pixel. However, its coverage is not complete for all SIDS, as some countries are only partially covered or not included at all.

Global land-cover product with fine classification system at 30 m - (GLC-FCS30D)

The GLC-FCS30D dataset offers a 30 m resolution global land-cover classification system that incorporates a detailed categorization of land cover types. This product distinguishes 16 global land-cover categories along with 14 additional detailed and regionally specific land-cover types.

Fig. 3: Screenshot of original GLC-FCS30D Land Cover on Antigua Island.

To generate these classifications, a locally adaptive random forest model was applied to each $5^\circ \times 5^\circ$ geographical tile, resulting in a land-cover dataset comprising 30 distinct categories (Zhang et al., 2020). The classification includes 10 forest types, 4 types of croplands, and 4 types of shrubland, among others.

Unlike GLAD, which provides data every five years, the GLC-FCS30D product offers historical data at five-year intervals from 1985 to 2000 and then annually from 2000 to 2022. Similar to GLAD, GLC-FCS30D does not provide complete coverage for all SIDS, with some countries either partially mapped or entirely absent from the dataset (Table 1). Additionally, this product has mapped approximately 10 million hectares less than GLAD in SIDS (Fig. 3).

Product comparison

To be able to compare these products one of the first activities that needs to be done is to homogenize the legend to the same categories. Since the objective is to explore usability in the context of UNCCD reporting, both maps were reclassified into the seven UNCCD classes (tree-covered, grassland, cropland, wetland, artificial, other land, and water body) according to Tables 3, 4 and 5 (see Technical Annex). It should be considered that in different SIDS there could be different ways of re-classifying each product in order to yield more accurate results.

A subset of years on which to run the comparison was selected considering those years involved in the UNCCD reporting process (or the closest ones that are available). This process not only allows for a direct comparison of both products using standardized categories but also enables the calculation of class areas, the extraction of transition statistics, and the assessment of how each product performs in land degradation assessment . Given the spatial distribution and environmental diversity of SIDS, it is crucial to evaluate these products across a range of countries that represent this variability.

Products were compared across different SIDS to explore which one could be more suitable for UNCCD reporting under different conditions. The analysis focused on the 30m products, identifying discrepancies in class areas, highlighting spatial agreements, assessing consistency with satellite imagery. Also, temporal transitions were analysed with the resulting degradation maps and related statistics for different periods. While Figure 4 shows an example for Antigua Island and the baseline period (2000-2015), all 40 SIDS (Table 1) and all the available periods for the reporting can be self-explored using the Land Cover Transition Tool presented in Chapter 2.

The next section highlights key findings and differences between the products.

Fig. 4: ESA CCI, GLC-FCS30D and GLAD land cover maps reclassified into the seven UNCCD classes for baseline period in Antigua Island and resulting degradation maps and graphs.

Main findings

As discussed above, while the products have different footprints and do not cover the same proportion of all 40 SIDS, we can calculate the cover areas of those 27 SIDS that have full overlap (Table 2).

LC category	ESA (ha)	GLAD (ha)	GLC_FCS30D (ha)	Difference (ha)
Tree covered	83,948,228	88,026,945	84,038,868	3,988,078
Grassland	8,129,851	8,365,211	7,096,920	1,268,291
Cropland	8,316,439	770,919	2,525,368	1,754,449
Wetland	4,114,994	5,221,006	2,412,023	2,808,983
Artificial	350,740	1,728,703	526,166	1,202,537
Other land	186,484	545,321	201,737	343,584
Water body	1,887,773	1,373,773	1,080,012	293,761

Table 2: Land cover categories for each product in 2015 and comparison of GLAD vs GLC-FCS30D

One of the most significant differences between products is in the way the Artificial category is obtained: Contextual classification vs Pixel Based classification. Overall, these represent the discrepancy between a Land Use vision vs Land Cover vision. The contextual version of GLAD shows almost four times more area than pixel based on GLC-FCS30D. While GLC-FCS30D labels in this category almost exclusively pixels occupied by “Impervious surfaces”, not considering green or not built-up areas, GLAD labels it as “Build-Up (Settlement)” and considers not only the man-made impervious surfaces, but the contextual nature of this class. Then, GLAD sums-up some green areas like parks, urban borders, vegetated spaces in sparse settlements together with impervious surfaces, showing solid urban areas. In contrast, GLC-FCS30D displays smaller and more fragmented artificial areas, mixed with vegetation cover, including individual pixels of cropland, grassland or forests inside the urban matrix.

Fig. 5: Screenshot of GLAD (left) and GLC-FCS30D (right) at the same area showing considerable differences, especially in urban-peri urban areas.

These differences must be particularly considered in transition and degradation analyses, since GLAD tends to underestimate changes into the urban matrix, while may overestimate urban growing in new

sparse or little built-up areas. On the other hand, GLC-FCS30D may detect small changes, without considering the contextual effect of urban growth.

A temporal analysis shows a significant aspect to consider regarding GLC-FCS30D. While the artificial area presents a net increase from 598,000 ha to 663,000 ha in the 2000 - 2015 period for all SIDS, there are gross changes showing 97,328 ha of artificial loss to other land covers (mostly croplands and tree-covers).

There is a huge overall difference shown in Table 2 for croplands: 770,000 ha. in GLAD vs 2.5 Mha in GLC-FCS30D. Grasslands also show significant differences, with 8.3 Mha in GLAD and 7.1 Mha in GLC-FCS30D.

Beyond the total areas, it is important to analyse the spatial consensus of the 2 products. The spatial analysis between cropland and grassland areas shows that there is approximately 5,927,000 ha of agreement. But also, there are 3,454,000 ha labelled as grassland in GLAD and cropland in GLC-FCS30D and the opposite combination accounts for just 45,000 ha.

Visually comparing these areas of disagreement with imagery reveals both grassland and cropland. No single product can be considered more accurate than the other for all SIDS. However, there are some countries where the GLAD dataset does not include cropland (or includes only a few hectares) and mistakenly classifies these areas as grassland or wetland.

Fig. 6: Example of area classified as grassland in GLAD and cropland in GLC-FCS30D in Cuba. **Left:** Google Earth image centered at coordinates 21.198774, -76.627412 showing grassland fields at west and cropland at the east. **Right:** Same area highlighting pixels labelled as grassland in GLAD and cropland in GLC-FCS30D in year 2015.

Wetlands show more disagreement (approximately 3.75 Mha in 2015) than agreements (1.46 Mha in 2015), and these are especially distributed on tree covered and artificial class in GLC-FCS30D. That shows a main difference in how each product considers wetland and tree covered areas, since GLAD includes mangroves and riparian forests and shrublands as wetlands, but for GLC-FCS30D these are limited to herbaceous vegetation. The Land Cover (LC) statistics are significantly affected by this difference in quite different countries like Guinea-Bissau, where GLAD classified over 260,000 ha as wetlands, while GLC-FCS30D mapped only 60,734 ha and Cape Verde with 33,452 ha and 959 ha respectively.

Forests or tree covered areas may be defined in different ways depending on the author or study objectives. As well as mangroves and riparian forests are considered wetland or forest in different works, open forests, shrublands and grasslands with scattered trees can be labelled both as grassland as tree covered. Then, from 6,940,000 ha classified as tree covered in GLC-FCS30D and other classes in GLAD, more than 3,003,000 ha were included as grassland and 3,006,000 ha as wetland

Given the above and observing that transitions between grassland and tree covered (both directions) are among the most important in hectares number for both products, it is able to ask whether that transitions are in fact man-made or an effect of environmental conditions, date of images, temporary vegetation condition, etcetera. It is an important aspect to consider since these discrepancies show quite different degradation maps (Fig. 7).

Fig. 7: An example in Trinidad and Tobago of how different degradation are maps in areas classified as grassland in GLAD and tree covered in GLC-FCS30D. Above left: Google earth image centered on coordinates 10.088465, -61.535238. Above right: highlighted pixels classified as grassland in GLAD and tree covered in GLC-FCS30D in 2015. Below: degradation maps (2000-2015) employing GLAD (left) and GLC-FCS30D (right).

Conclusions

The analysis clearly demonstrates that beyond shared technical characteristics, each global land cover product performs differently across countries due to their unique environmental conditions and landscape complexity. A product that aligns well with visual satellite interpretation in one region may perform poorly in another. Similarly, while one product may excel in accurately classifying specific land cover categories, it may underperform or misclassify others, introducing substantial variability in land statistics.

However, classification accuracy alone is not sufficient. For SDG 15.3.1 and UNCCD reporting, the ultimate objective is to generate reliable *land degradation maps*, which are fundamentally based on detecting land cover transitions over time. A land cover dataset that appears consistent or visually accurate in a single year may still produce misleading degradation trends if its temporal consistency is poor or if classification shifts are not meaningful in the context of land change processes. Therefore, datasets must be assessed not just for how well they classify land in isolation, but for how reliably they capture change and support valid degradation assessments across reporting periods.

In recognition of this need, the Land Cover Comparison Tool for Small Island Developing States was developed. This tool enables users to go beyond static evaluations and conduct dynamic analyses—comparing overlap between datasets, generating masks of agreement and disagreement, evaluating gains and losses, and visualizing transition matrices and degradation outcomes. Such a tool is essential for evidence-based selection and interpretation of land cover products, ensuring both spatial accuracy and temporal reliability in land degradation monitoring for SIDS.

Chapter 2: Land Cover Transition Tool

Land Cover Comparison Tool for Small Island Developing States is being developed to support decision making and comparison of land cover transition analysis with different available products for UNCCD reporting in SIDS. The tool is entirely developed in Google Earth Engine platform and is available for free use here: <https://apacheta.projects.earthengine.app/view/compare-lct-sids>

Considering reporting periods defined by UNCCD, the tool offers the possibility to evaluate GLAD and GLC_FCS30D for those years or the closest ones available and compare results to default ESA CCI-LC. Reporting periods and product availability can be found in Table 2.

UNCCD Reporting period	Initial-final year	Product availability		
		ESA CCI-LC	GLAD	GLC-FCS30D
Baseline	2000-2015	2000-2015	2000-2015	2000-2015
Period 1	2015-2019	2015-2019	2015-2020	2015-2019
Period 2	2015-2023	2015-2020	2015-2020	2015-2022
Longest available	2000-2023	2000-2020	2000-2020	2000-2022

Table 2: Reporting periods and product availability by year.

The Land Cover Transition Tool is divided into two panels and a map area (Fig. 8). Left panel allows setting the tool, choosing language, SIDS or administrative unit of interest and target year for LC comparison. Also, for each product, it is possible to select a period for temporal comparison as well as spatial analysis in disagreement categories between products. Settings chosen in the left panel will be displayed in the map area and the results panel located on the right.

Fig. 8: Screenshot of an overview of Land Cover Comparison Tool.

Selecting a SIDS centres the map on the interest area, while stats and maps are shown for the same area for local or regional analyses. Optionally, it is possible to select other administrative units or load a single feature asset by entering the asset ID. Another option is to draw an area of interest by using the Drawing toolbox. If no one SIDS is selected in the first step, results will be displayed for all SIDS.

Land Cover Comparison Tool for Small Island Developing States

This application is being developed to support decision making and comparison of land cover transition analysis with different available products for UNCCD reporting in SIDS

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Close info panel

English

Choose a SIDS from the list below or click on the map to get statistics. (*)

Dominica

Select Administrative Unit

Select which layer you want to click on. (*)

None

Alternatively, if you want to calculate stats for a preloaded single feature asset please enter the asset id and click on the button to load the asset from GEE

GEE asset id

AOI Layers

- SIDS
- Administrative Units
- ESA 10m (2021)
- ESRI 10m (2023)

LC products comparison

Fig. 9: Screenshot of left panel and map area

Additionally, it is possible to add as base map ESA 10m and ESRI 10m LC products of the years 2021 and 2023, respectively.

Below, in the same panel, the "LC Products Comparison" box allows users to select a target year for visually comparing GLAD and GLC-FCS30D on the map. The equal mask layer is a white layer that covers agreement pixels between the maps, making it easier to focus on areas of disagreement.

Fig. 10: LC products comparison box with equal mask activated and 2000 as target year (above). Map area showing GLAD (left) and GLC-FCS30D (right) covered by equal mask.

Next, there are three boxes, on each product, that allow us to make temporally comparisons by product and analyse transitions and degradation. By selecting a period, according to UNCCD reporting periods, different options are displayed, allowing to turn on initial and final LC for the selected period, as well as gains, losses and degradation maps.

Fig. 11: Above: GLC-FCS30D gains (left) and losses (right) for period 2000-2015 in Singapore. Below: Degradation map for the same period and area (left) and GLC-FCS30D transitions box.

In the Multi-Criteria Analysis box, users can spatially compare both products by selecting a combination of classes from each dataset. The result is a mask that highlights pixels where the chosen combination is met. For example, if the user selects grassland in GLAD and tree-covered areas in GLC-FCS30D, the map will display a layer highlighting pixels labeled as grassland in GLAD and tree-covered in GLC-FCS30D, along with the area in hectares.

Fig. 12: Multi-Criteria analysis box, showing a combination of grassland in GLAD and Tree covered in GLC-FCS30D and the resulting layer in the map area.

The right panel displays statistics for the analyses selected in the left panel, showing the name of the selected area, total area in hectares and interactive charts.

First, the Land Cover Comparison box displays a bar chart, comparing the area by class and product for a target year. By panning over the bars, a label with the area calculated for the class is displayed and the complete table is downloadable through the upper right symbol.

Fig. 13: Right panel showing name of interest area, total area and LC products comparison box.

Next, there are three product boxes, one per product. Each one displays a column chart of land cover change, showing total area in the initial and final year by class.

That is followed by a Net LC changes chart. In this, each class is coloured in green if its area grew up and red if decreased in the period, and the size of the bar represents the net change. Furthermore, the top and bottom of bars indicate total area at beginning or end of the period.

Fig. 14: GLAD box showing Land cover change chart for the period 2000-2015 and corresponding net LC changes chart.

A transition matrix is presented as a table, where the initial class is in rows while final is in columns. The area for each combination of classes is in hectares.

2000/2015	Tree covered	Grassland	Cropland	Wetland	Artificial	Other land	Water body
Tree covered	3,283,050.75	97,334.4	4,293.3	22,603.22	10,743.92	0.16	813.88
Grassland	71,807.27	3,361,352.34	174,375.61	1,515.52	42,005.21	12.55	184.15
Cropland	27,539.7	598,637.73	1,077,663.29	52,122.67	9,352.78	9.03	208.59
Wetland	17,110.9	5,912.79	31,794.87	1,329,739.25	4,257.33	855.62	63,815.48
Artificial	6.73	18.76	0.59	0.17	516,966.51	0	0
Other land	0.33	41.41	9.02	2,685.9	29.96	157.02	493.37
Water body	271.62	2,091.76	194.19	30,157.91	190.38	784.7	243,093.13

Fig. 15: Transition matrix showing LC changes calculated on GLAD for the period 2000-2015 in Cuba.

Finally, a pie chart calculated from the above transition matrix is presented, showing the area for each class of degradation analysis in percentage and hectares for the country.

Fig. 16: Pie chart showing proportion of three classes of degradation analysis.

Chapter 3: Examples in different SIDS

Beyond the general insights and key findings presented in Chapter One, it is crucial to understand how these products vary across different geographic contexts and environmental conditions. To explore this, examples of 7 different SIDS were analysed by using the Land Cover Transition Tool. For each case general statistics were calculated, making spatial comparisons and evaluating temporal transitions and degradation analysis performance. The key findings below highlight the most significant discrepancies between products and their potential impact on temporal transition and degradation assessments within the framework of UNCCD reporting.

Saint Lucia

Both maps show a high prevalence of tree covered class, covering more than 43,000 ha, followed by artificial, though with significant differences in area. Comparing the years 2020 (GLAD) and 2022 (GLC-FCS30D), 20.83% of the classified surface shows disagreements. Of this area, 48.52% corresponds to pixels classified as forest in GLC-FCS30D but as artificial in GLAD, primarily in urban interface zones with high vegetation cover.

Fig. 17: ESA CCI, GLC-FCS30D and GLAD land cover maps reclassified into the seven UNCCD classes for baseline period in Saint Lucia and resulting degradation maps and graphs.

Fig. 18: Bar chart showing total area by class and product in Saint Lucia.

Fig. 19: Above: Google Earth image (left) centered on coordinates -61.00598, 13.97326, showing mixed urban-vegetated areas and the same area on a Landsat 8 image from 2022 (right). Middle: View of the same place in reclassified GLC-FCS30D (left) and GLAD (right) products. Below: Multi-Criteria analysis highlighting pixels classified as forest in GLC-FCS30D and artificial in GLAD.

Nevertheless, one main aspect to consider, particularly in Saint Lucia, is that GLC-FCS30D mistakenly labels some places as artificial and other classes, probably due to clouds in images.

Fig. 20: Above: Google Earth image (-61.01093, 13.86288), where areas of forest and grassland are identified. **Below:** Same classified by GLC-FCS30D as artificial, water body and others.

The second major difference between the products, at the area level, lies in pixels classified as forests in GLC-FCS30D and as grasslands in GLAD, which account for 23.89% of the total disagreements. Visual interpretation reveals that, more of these areas show a high percentage of low vegetation cover, including pastures, shrublands, crops, and, to a lesser extent, open forests and areas with sparse vegetation.

Fig. 21: Above: Google Earth image (-60.928582, 13.941696), where areas of low vegetation are identified. Below: Same sector where these areas are classified as forest by GLC-FCS30D and grassland by GLAD.

Fig. 22: Above: Google Earth image (-60.907906, 14.028494), where crop plots surrounded by forest can be seen. Below: Same sector where it is identified that the cultivated area was classified as forest by GLC-FCS30D and grassland by GLAD.

Fig. 23: Above: Google Earth image (-60.906569, 14.044614), showing areas with sparse vegetation cover. Below: Same area where the cultivated area is classified as forest by GLC-FCS30D and grassland by GLAD.

Despite classification differences, degradation in the period 2000-2015 results in approximately 3% whatever product is employed. That degradation percentage is mainly due to growing in artificial areas in replacement of tree covered and grassland. However, the location of changes was quite different, while GLAD shows artificial gains as solid patches at peripheral areas, GLC-FCS30D presents them as scattered, individual pixels distributed across both into cities as at outskirts. This pattern is similar in different analysis periods.

Fig. 24: Above: Gain maps for period 2000-2015 centered in coordinates -60.94433, 14.0714, from GLAD (left) and GLC-FCS30D (right). Below: Degradation maps in the same area from GLAD (left) and GLC-FCS30D (right).

Antigua And Barbuda

In Antigua and Barbuda, the differences among products are highly significant, affecting up to 57.77% of the total area. Unlike other SIDS, where differences tend to concentrate in one or two classes, here, most land cover classes show substantial variations, sometimes doubling or even more from one product to another (Fig. 25).

For example, GLC-FCS30D reports twice the forest area of GLAD and nearly nine times more cropland. Conversely, GLAD classifies a much larger area as artificial (13,675 ha), grassland (8,995 ha), and wetland (4,794 ha) compared to GLC-FCS30D (4,680 ha, 176 ha, and 1,338 ha, respectively). However, a more detailed analysis of the spatial distribution of these differences reveals additional patterns.

Fig. 25: Bar chart showing total area by class and product in Antigua and Barbuda.

The greatest spatial difference in surface area occupies **23.77% of the pixels in disagreement and corresponds to areas classified as forest in GLC-FCS30D and grassland in GLAD**. Visual interpretation indicates that these areas generally correspond to forests that appear to be low in height, open shrublands with a high proportion of bare ground and/or herbaceous vegetation. In some cases, the coverage of woody plants appears to be sparse, with predominating herbaceous vegetation or bare ground.

Fig. 26: Overview of Antigua and Barbuda highlighting areas classified as grassland in GLAD and tree covered in GLC-FCS30D.

Fig. 27: Above: Google Earth image (-61.807215, 17.612341) showing open or fragmented forest areas. Below: This image highlights pixels labelled as forest by GLC-FCS30D and grassland by GLAD, marked in fuchsia.

Fig. 28: Above: Google Earth image (-61.786833, 17.586109) of shrubland/grassland areas with low tree cover. Middle: Sentinel 2 Image from the same location. Below: The same area highlighting pixels classified as forest by GLC-FCS30D and as grassland by GLAD.

In Antigua Island, some different cases can be observed, where low but dense forests have been classified as forest by GLC-FCS30D and as grassland by GLAD.

Fig. 29: Above: Google Earth image (-61.782616, 17.116014), showing a dense low height forest. Middle: Sentinel 2 image (median of year 2022) showing the same place. Below: Image highlighting area classified as forest by GLC-FCS30D and as grassland by GLAD.

But the difference in forest area is not only due to disagreement in forest-grassland between products, but 5,090 ha that were classified as forest in GLC-FCS30D, were classified as artificial in GLAD.

Distribution of these pixels is very similar to that observed in Saint Lucia, prevailing in peri-urban and urban areas with high tree cover mixed with built-up areas.

Fig. 30: **Left:** Google Earth image (-61.764409, 17.02286), showing an urban area with significant tree cover. **Right:** The same area, highlighting regions classified as forest by GLC-FCS30D and artificial by GLAD.

Third, with 14.94% of disagreement pixels, are areas classified as cropland by GLC-FCS30D and artificial by GLAD. Similar to forest/artificial areas, these pixels are distributed in peri-urban contexts and are mostly observed as landscaped areas or zones with low or sparse vegetation, such as vacant lots, small landfills, and parks. In some extreme cases, GLAD shows wide artificial areas where it has just a few sparse buildings.

Fig. 31: Above left: Google Earth image (-61.730428, 17.064858), showing an area with a high proportion of open/not built spaces. **Above right:** Sentinel 2 image of the same area (2022 median). **Below:** The same shot, highlighting regions classified as cropland by GLC-FCS30D and artificial by GLAD.

Even if degradation statistics didn't result in a large difference, it is clear that spatial distribution is significantly affected by product selection. While degradation/improvement is driven mainly by changes from tree covered or grassland to artificial and grassland to cropland in GLAD, GLC-FCS30D may also show large artificial losses or changes from forest to cropland.

2000/2015	Tree covered	Grassland	Cropland	Wetland	Artificial	Other land	Water body
Tree covered	13,218.76	323.74	5.04	75.79	297.33	3.53	0
Grassland	113.62	9,328.33	132.76	19.79	778.45	0.43	1.69
Cropland	10.27	65.84	36.52	18.11	5.64	0	0
Wetland	42.5	45.17	12.48	4,647.79	178.43	78.43	355.24
Artificial	0	0	0	0	11,682.26	0	0
Other land	7.78	3.03	0	172.66	3.21	96.14	45.33
Water body	1.28	15.78	10.35	129.57	3.47	12.79	3,264.5

2000/2015	Tree covered	Grassland	Cropland	Wetland	Artificial	Other land	Water body
Tree covered	27,304.15	5.93	277.43	218.74	564.81	7.64	13.9
Grassland	2.05	164.73	0.51	0.34	0.94	0.09	0
Cropland	132.83	0.34	6,362.91	36.54	472.1	0.43	2.18
Wetland	213.02	0.67	45.23	848.38	16.29	2.33	484.75
Artificial	465.46	1.59	589.93	16.96	2,942.74	3.09	4.71
Other land	2.58	0.09	0.22	2.29	2.85	27.16	0
Water body	54.42	0	23.02	269.1	3.84	0.46	3,143.45

Fig. 32: Above: degradation map for period 2000-2015 based on GLAD (left) and GLC-FCS30D (right). Middle: Transition matrix for the same period in GLAD. Below: Transition matrix for the same period in GLC-FCS30D.

Trinidad and Tobago

Trinidad and Tobago exhibits a high prevalence of tree-covered areas, with 79% in GLC-FCS30D and 65% in GLAD. Artificial cover ranks second, with minor disagreements compared to previous cases, likely due to the presence of large and dense urban areas, where GLC-FCS30D does not classify other categories. However, significant differences exist in grasslands (3.05% in GLC-FCS30D vs. 10.67% in GLAD), croplands (7.62% in GLC-FCS30D, 12 times higher than GLAD), and wetlands (5.84% in GLAD vs. 0.84% in GLC-FCS30D).

Fig. 33: ESA CCI, GLC-FCS30D and GLAD land cover maps reclassified into the seven UNCCD classes for baseline period in Trinidad and Tobago and resulting degradation maps and graphs.

Fig. 34: Bar chart showing total area by class and product in Trinidad and Tobago.

The area of differing pixels between maps accounts for 24.83%, more than half of which correspond to areas classified as forest in GLC-FCS30D and other categories in GLAD. Most of those are areas classified as forest in GLC-FCS30D and grassland in GLAD, representing 22.07% of the differences. In the southern part of the country, this discrepancy is notable due to its extent, "smooth/solid" texture, and geometrically defined edges, identified in satellite images as shrublands or shorter forests. According to the FireCCI51 dataset (Chuvieco et al., 2018), these areas experienced fires in April 2017, as confirmed by Landsat 8 images from the same month.

Fig. 35: Above: Google Earth image centered on coordinates 10.084910, -61.509800 (left) showing forest and grassland areas clearly delimited and same shot, showing the area classified as forest in GLC-FCS30D and grassland in GLAD (right). **Below:** Landsat 8 image of the area where the burned zone is visible coincident to grassland area observed as grassland.

Beyond this specific case, most pixels classified as forest by GLC-FCS30D and grassland by GLAD correspond to the grassland category. They are generally distributed along forest edges or in small-scale horticultural areas surrounded by trees.

Fig. 36: Above: Google Earth image showing areas dominated by grassland with low tree cover (left). Sentinel 2 image of the same area (right). **Below:** Mask showing the area classified as forest in GLC-FCS30D and grassland in GLAD.

Areas classified as forest in GLC-FCS30D and artificial in GLAD represent 20.92% of the disagreement area, ranking second in discrepancies between these products in Trinidad and Tobago. As observed in other countries, these differences are clearly distributed in peri-urban areas or regions where high proportions of vegetative cover are mixed with buildings.

Fig. 37: Above: Google Earth image of an outskirts area (left). Sentinel 2 image from the same place (right). **Below:** Mask showing the area classified as forest in GLC-FCS30D and artificial in GLAD.

Fig. 38: Spatial distribution of areas classified as forest by GLC-FCS30D and artificial by GLAD.

Another significant difference, encompassing 15.53% of the differing pixels, occurs in areas classified as forest by GLC-FCS30D and wetland by GLAD. A large patch of this class is observed to the east of the main island, which when analysed by photointerpretation is clearly identified as a wetland. GLAD's sensitivity to wetlands is notable, achieving generally good identification, although possibly overestimated as some cropland plots are erroneously classified as wetlands, especially at the wetland border.

Fig. 39: Above: Google Earth image (-61.06453, 10.37935), showing a wetland surrounded by forest (left). Sentinel 2 image (Year 2022 median) of the same area (right). **Below:** The same area, highlighting regions classified as forest by GLC-FCS30D and wetland by GLAD.

Cropland and pastureland often overlap in land cover maps. In this case, 13.66% of disagreement areas correspond to pixels classified as cropland in GLC-FCS30D and grassland in GLAD, while the reverse situation accounts for only 1.05%. At first glance, no clear trends are observed, as these disagreement areas include both clearly identifiable cropland and pastureland, as well as peri-urban spaces dominated by low vegetation.

Fig. 40: Left: Google Earth image (-61.400273, 10.327334), showing numerous cropland plots. **Centre:** Sentinel 2 image of the same area (2022 median). **Right:** Regions classified as cropland by GLC-FCS30D and pastureland by GLAD highlighted.

Fig. 41: Left: Google Earth image (-61.45733, 10.40175), showing a peri-urban area with open spaces dominated by low vegetation. **Centre:** Sentinel 2 image of the same area (2022 median). **Right:** The same area, highlighting regions classified as cropland by GLC-FCS30D and pastureland by GLAD.

Respecting LC temporal transition, a significant difference between products exists in cropland. GLAD shows a positive change in cropland of 91.61 ha, whilst in GLC-FCS30D this change represents 3,232.76 ha. Mainly, these changes in GLC-FCS30D respond to deforestation activities, not necessarily for agricultural use but transformation to grassland, possibly as grazing lands, and waste dumps. On the other hand, these changes are mapped by GLAD as grassland (6,394 ha), but this is not evident in the net change plot, probably due to a higher rate of transition from grassland to artificial.

Fig. 42: Above: Landsat images (coordinates: -61.06418, 10.6508) in natural colour, depicting a tree-covered area in 2000 (left) and the same area in 2015 (right), where some parts have been deforested. **Below:** Gains for each class for the period 2000-2015 on GLAD (left) and GLC-FCS30D (right).

Cape Verde

Both products show a high predominance of grassland, at 52 and 67% in GLC-FCS30D and GLAD respectively, while the "other lands" class occupies 38.9% and 17.7% of the surface.

Fig. 43: ESA CCI, GLC-FCS30D and GLAD land cover maps reclassified into the seven UNCCD classes for baseline period in Santiago Island (Cape Verde) and resulting degradation maps and graphs.

LC GLAD Land Cover 2000 - GLC_FCS30D ATG 2000

Fig. 44: Bar chart showing total area by class and product in Cape Verde.

A key issue is that artificial cover is not represented in GLAD; instead, built-up areas are labelled as grasslands or wetlands under UNCCD categories. To determine whether these errors stemmed from the reclassification process, urban areas were identified using satellite imagery and overlaid with the original GLAD map. This analysis confirmed that the original map does not classify built-up areas in the country. Instead, most of these areas are labelled as Semi-arid short vegetation (12, 15, and 17) or Sparse vegetation (107, 111, and 116).

Fig. 45: Above: Google Earth image (-23.665593, 15.096422) centered on an urbanized area. **Middle:** The same area in the reclassified GLAD map, showing pixels classified as grasslands and wetlands. **Below:** Original GLAD map showing various classes belonging to sparse and semi-arid vegetation groups.

Additionally, rocky areas formed by volcanic eruptions tend to be classified mainly as wetlands and grasslands in GLAD, and as water bodies in GLC-FCS30D. While this does not represent a significant surface area at the country level, it may be an aspect to consider in other islands.

Fig. 46: **Left:** Overview of Ilha Do Fogo in a 2022 Sentinel 2 image showing dark traces of volcanic eruptions. **Centre:** Same shot mapped in GLC-FCS30D. **Right:** Same shot mapped in GLAD.

In terms of product comparison, 26.58% of the pixels differ in their assigned class, 62.86% of which are classified as "other lands" in GLC-FCS30D and grasslands in GLAD. In an environment like Cape Verde, such differences between products are expected, as the way classes are defined can lead to the same cover being classified differently. Indeed, the spatial distribution of these differences seems to mark a broad boundary between the two classes. Furthermore, it should be noted that these are dynamic landscapes, so the timing and set of images used for map creation could have a significant impact on the results. For this case, field information and/or specific products might be required.

Fig. 47: Maps comparison in Santo Antão Island. **Left:** GLC-FCS30D; **Right:** GLAD.

Fig. 48: Distribution of areas classified as "other lands" in GLC-FCS30D and grasslands in GLAD in the islands of Santo Antão (top left), São Vicente (top right), and São Nicolau (bottom). Each image shows the total area of these combined categories by island.

Similarly, the "other lands" class in GLC-FCS30D is classified as wetlands in GLAD, accounting for 18% of the discrepancy surface. These areas generally have highly sparse vegetation cover, which could be scattered shrubs or low herbaceous vegetation, often linked to volcanic rock or traces of volcanic eruptions.

Fig. 49: Above: Google Earth image (-25.09888, 17.01085) of a predominantly bare soil area. **Middle:** Sentinel 2 image of the same area (2022 median), confirming what is observed in high-definition imagery. **Below:** Demarcation of areas classified as "other lands" by GLC-FCS30D and wetlands by GLAD.

9.47% of the product's differences occur in areas classified as grasslands in GLC-FCS30D and wetlands in GLAD. Generally, these belong to zones with very sparse vegetation, such as bare soil, the hillsides of Pico Do Fogo volcano, and low, sparse pastures. Additionally, agricultural areas are almost exclusively classified under this combination of classes, with no pixels classified as cropland in none of the products.

Fig. 50: **Left:** Google Earth image (-23.52772, 15.11383) in an agricultural area. **Centre:** Demarcation of areas classified as grasslands in GLC-FCS30D and wetlands in GLAD. **Right:** Sentinel 2 image of the same area (2022 median), clearly identifying the agricultural zone.

Since, grassland, wetland, and other land classes are dynamic, they may transition between each other not only due to human activity but also because of variations in environmental conditions, image acquisition dates, and class definitions. This leads to a high rate of change between 2000 and 2015 in both maps but a low agreement on which areas have changed. For instance, a green basin where sparse shrubs and trees grew during this period was classified as grassland in GLC-FCS30D but as other land in GLAD in 2000. By 2015, GLAD indicates an increase in grassland for the area, whereas GLC-FCS30D does not.

The opposite case is also common, and depending on the area, one or the other may detect different changes.

Fig. 51: Above: Landsat images (-22.96428, 16.75405) in natural colour, showing a basin with low vegetation coverage in 2000 (left) and the presence of some riverside vegetation in 2015 (right). **Middle:** Land cover (LC) products from GLAD (left) and GLC-FCS30D (right). **Below:** Gains for each class during the 2000–2015 period according to GLAD (left) and GLC-FCS30D (right).

Of course, degradation maps are quite different

Fig. 52: Degradation map for the previous example.

Barbados

In this country, 48.1% of the area presents disagreements between products, gathered in tree covered and grassland.

Fig. 53: ESA CCI, GLC-FCS30D and GLAD land cover maps reclassified into the seven UNCCD classes for baseline period in Barbados and resulting degradation maps and graphs.

Fig. 54: Bar chart showing total area by class and product in Barbados.

Different to most cases, where there is not a clear difference between maps to consider one of them better than the other for the reporting purpose, in Barbados there is. Unlike the rest of the countries, in Barbados GLC-FCS30D shows more artificial area than GLAD, most of these differing areas are in fact grasslands and croplands, thus it is evident that GLC-FCS30D is overestimating artificial area.

Fig. 55: Spatial distribution of pixels classified as artificial in GLC-FCS30D and other classes in GLAD.

Fig. 56: Above: Google Earth image showing mainly crop plots. Below: Area classified as artificial in GLC-FCS30D and cropland in GLAD.

On the other hand, as observed in other cases, contextual classification of artificial areas in GLAD tends to overlap with other coverages, like forests.

Fig. 57: Above: Google Earth image (-59.620252, 13.273674) showing an interface area between urban and countryside (left). Sentinel 2 image (2022 median) of the same area (right). **Below:** Area classified as artificial in GLAD, and tree covered in GLC-FCS30D highlighted over the first image.

Nevertheless, tree covered is overestimated in GLC-FCS30D, showing 2.5 times more area of this class than GLAD, encompassing wide cropland and grassland areas, which are better classified

Fig. 58: Left: Google Earth image (-59.61625, 13.31786) on an agricultural/pastureland area. **Right:** Same area highlighting pixels classified as forest by GLC-FCS30D and cropland or grassland by GLAD.

When LC transitions were analysed, it was found that overestimation of artificial class is not only a problem for one year, in 2000 the area in this category is even more than 2015 and 2022, reaching 32,696 ha (the whole country covers 43,466 ha). It means a loss in artificial areas of 7,291 ha in the period 2000-2015, which may meaningfully affect the degradation statistics.

Fig. 59: Above: Overview on Barbados GLC-FCS30D map for year 2000 (left). Losses for each class in the period 2000-2015 (right). **Below:** Degradation map 2000-2015 employing GLC-FCS30D products (left) and corresponding pie chart (right).

Timor-Leste

The most noticeable difference observed in Timor-Leste is in grassland and cropland categories, where GLC-FCS30D shows almost 320,000 ha more crops than GLAD. Moreover, GLAD classifies more than 250.000 ha of grassland, while GLC-FCS30D only 46,000 ha.

Fig. 60: ESA CCI, GLC-FCS30D and GLAD land cover maps reclassified into the seven UNCCD classes for baseline period in an area of Timor Leste and resulting degradation maps and graphs.

Fig. 61: Bar chart showing total area by class and product in Timor-Leste.

The overlapping of areas classified as cropland by GLC-FCS30D and grassland by GLAD, occupies more than 170,000 ha, which are mostly observed on satellite image as grassland or open shrublands, so it's possible to say that cropland is overestimated on GLC-FCS30D.

Fig. 62: Left: Google Earth image (126.50285, -8.48613) on a grassland/shrubland land area. Right: Same area highlighting pixels classified as cropland by GLC-FCS30D and grassland by GLAD.

But GLC-FCS30D cropland occupies much more area than GLAD grassland, then, GLC-FCS30D cropland overlaps to other classes of GLAD. The most of these corresponds to tree covered areas for GLAD and represents 25% of the differences between the maps. When these areas are compared against satellite images, they can be observed as deciduous and open forests.

Fig. 63: Left: Google Earth image (124.43435, -9.215543) on an open and deciduous forest area. Right: Same area highlighting pixels classified as cropland by GLC-FCS30D and tree covered by GLAD.

For artificial areas, GLC-FCS30D looks more accurate, since GLAD shows watercourses and bare ground as artificial. This, added to contextual classification, results in 7 times more artificial area classified by GLAD than GLC-FCS30D.

Fig. 64: Above: Google Earth image (125.33203, -9.24564) where three watercourses can be observed. Middle: GLAD LC showing parts of the rivers as artificial. Below: Same area on GLC-FCS30D.

Guinea-Bissau

With a high predominance of tree covered areas in both products, Guinea-Bissau shows huge differences in the total area of most of the classes. Disagreement area reaches 30% in this country, where half corresponds to tree covered in GLC-FCS30D and grassland in GLAD.

Fig. 65: ESA CCI, GLC-FCS30D and GLAD land cover maps reclassified into the seven UNCCD classes for baseline period in Guinea-Bissau and resulting degradation maps and graphs.

Fig. 66: Bar chart showing total area by class and product in Guinea-Bissau.

These areas of disagreement can contain forest as well as grassland and crops, including zones where these three coverages are mixed as a mosaic, but are almost completely classified as tree covered or grassland.

Fig. 67: Above: Google Earth image (-15.856412, 12.185775) showing a mixed area of forests, croplands and grazelands. **Below:** Same area highlighting pixels classified as tree covered by GLC-FCS30D and grassland by GLAD.

Guinea-Bissau is a good example to analyse how wetlands are mapped by each product. While GLAD includes more than 260,000 ha of this class, GLC-FCS30D has just 60,734 ha. The difference is mainly distributed on tree covered and grassland. Areas classified as wetland by GLAD and tree covered by GLC-FCS30D occupies approximately 183,000 ha and correspond mostly to riparian forests and shrublands. Some cases include wetland zones or cropland without forests.

Fig. 68: Above: Google Earth image (-15.20298, 11.75641) showing a river and riparian forests. **Below:** Same area highlighting pixels classified as tree covered by GLC-FCS30D and wetland by GLAD.

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Technical annex

Table 2: Reclassification from ESA CCI to UNCCD land cover classes. Cell colours correspond to the default product colour.

ESA CCI LC class	UNCCD class
Tree cover, broadleaved, evergreen, closed to open (>15%)	Tree covered
Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, closed to open (>15%)	
Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, closed (>40%)	
Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, open (15-40%)	
Tree cover, needleleaved, evergreen, closed to open (>15%)	
Tree cover, needleleaved, evergreen, closed (>40%)	
Tree cover, needleleaved, evergreen, open (15-40%)	
Tree cover, needleleaved, deciduous, closed to open (>15%)	
Tree cover, needleleaved, deciduous, closed (>40%)	
Tree cover, needleleaved, deciduous, open (15-40%)	
Tree cover, mixed leaf type (broadleaved and needleleaved)	
Mosaic tree and shrub (>50%) / herbaceous cover (<50%)	
Mosaic natural vegetation (tree, shrub, herbaceous cover) (>50%) / cropland (<50%)	
Mosaic herbaceous cover (>50%) / tree and shrub (<50%)	
Shrubland	
Evergreen shrubland	
Deciduous shrubland	
Grassland	
Lichens and mosses	
Sparse vegetation (tree, shrub, herbaceous cover) (<15%)	
Sparse shrub (<15%)	
Sparse herbaceous cover (<15%)	
Cropland, rainfed	Cropland
Herbaceous cover	
Tree or shrub cover	
Cropland, irrigated or post-flooding	
Mosaic cropland (>50%) / natural vegetation (tree, shrub, herbaceous cover) (<50%)	

Tree cover, flooded, fresh or brakish water	Wetland
Tree cover, flooded, saline water	
Shrub or herbaceous cover, flooded, fresh/saline/brakish water	
Urban areas	Artificial
Bare areas	Other lands
Consolidated bare areas	
Unconsolidated bare areas	
Permanent snow and ice	
Water bodies	Water body

Table 3: Reclassification from GLAD to UNCCD land cover classes. Cell colours correspond to the default product colour.

GLAD LC class	UNCCD class
Tree cover 5-19 m (dry)	Tree covered
Tree cover 20-25+ m (dry)	
Tree cover 5-19 m (wet)	
Tree cover 20-25+ m (wet)	
Semi-arid short vegetation (11-75%, dry)	Grassland
Dense short vegetation (75-100%, dry)	
Tree cover 3-4 m (dry)	
Cropland	Cropland
Sparse vegetation (11-75%, wet)	Wetland
Dense short vegetation (75-100%, wet)	
Tree cover 3-4 m (wet)	
Open surface water (20-70% of year)	
Built-up	Artificial
True desert (0-10% short vegetation, dry)	Other lands
Salt pan (0-11% short vegetation, wet)	
Snow/ice	
Open surface water (70-100% of year)	Water body
Ocean	

Table 4: Reclassification from GLC-FCS30D to UNCCD land cover classes. Cell colours correspond to the default product colour.

GLC-FCS30D LC Class	UNCCD class
Open evergreen broadleaved forest	Tree covered
Closed evergreen broadleaved forest	
Open deciduous broadleaved forest (0.15<fc<0.4)	
Closed deciduous broadleaved forest (fc>0.4)	
Open evergreen needle-leaved forest (0.15< fc <0.4)	
Closed evergreen needle-leaved forest (fc >0.4)	
Open deciduous needle-leaved forest (0.15< fc <0.4)	
Closed deciduous needle-leaved forest (fc >0.4)	
Open mixed leaf forest (broadleaved and needle-leaved)	
Closed mixed leaf forest (broadleaved and needle-leaved)	
Mangrove	
Shrubland	Grassland
Evergreen shrubland	
Deciduous shrubland	
Grassland	
Lichens and mosses	
Sparse vegetation (fc<0.15)	
Sparse shrubland (fc<0.15)	
Sparse herbaceous (fc<0.15)	Cropland
Rainfed cropland	
Herbaceous cover cropland	
Tree or shrub cover (Orchard) cropland	
Irrigated cropland	Wetland
Swamp	
Marsh	
Flooded flat	
Saline	Artificial
Impervious surfaces	
Bare areas	Other lands

Consolidated bare areas	
Unconsolidated bare areas	
Permanent ice and snow	
Water body	Water body